

BM 5102 | ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR

Semester 1 | 2020/2021

Reflective Critique Report

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Throughout this semester, I gain plenty of eye-opening and valuable knowledge. In this level of education, I get to see the insights, the rush, and the pressure I have heard from other people come before me. However, the current pandemic contributes along with the downside of my studies. In the global context, Covid-19 has affected every individual. Some may face different types of stress and anxiety to depression due to the disruption of the social system (Karunathilake, 2020). Personally, the reason for pursuing a master's study is hoping to increase the chances of having better and stable jobs in the future. This mindset is typically normal as according to Musa & Idris (2020), Bruneian youths prefer prestigious and stable jobs with high salaries. According to BBC News (2019, July 09), Brunei is one of the highest standards of living around the world due to its oil and gas reserves. Furthermore, Bandar Seri Begawan ranks 63rd most expensive city out of 135 cities globally, in which it jumped 10 steps from 2019 and second highest in Southeast Asia (Azlan, 2020). Logically, the higher the standard of living, the higher quality of life. This will lead to the youngsters setting their minds to have a 'real' and 'proper' job with high paid salary, and preparing themselves for adulthood.

Getting into this module, other than peer reviews, class discussions, and consultations, there are two big chunks of graded assignments in which *group work case studies* and *individual analysis* are given. Both assignments have their own ups and downs and it really reflects on who I am as a person particularly as a master student. As related to my individual analysis paper, my motivation felt like a rollercoaster where one day I will be motivated to do work and other days will be not. Sometimes I feel demotivated having a lot of piling assignments, not really knowing what or how to start. I did not know how overwhelming this whole thing was at first. Before the start of this semester, I keep myself from wasting time rationally. I figured after; I need to put more effort than just that. It is the amount of consistency and persistence to execute in everything you do. However, everyday is not as easy, especially when you feel like you do not do the perfect version of the effort you have given into your work. It really felt like you are panicking which leads to overthinking and it does drain your energy like you physically get tired. I might say if you feel something or a burden inside you, I tried having a conversation with your friends and just let it all out thus, it does work somehow. The goal is to be your best self even if we do not get to be the person who we expected to be, we will eventually get there. This can relate to Maslow's hierarchy of needs. This theory assumes that human needs are arranged in hierarchical importance (Griffin, Phillips & Gully, 2016). According to this theory, there are five different levels of needs as people must seek the basic need in life first and then move up to the highest potential of needs. This includes physiological needs (food, shelter, and clothing), security needs (feeling secure with family and the circle of society they live in as well as safety), love and belonging needs (the feel of receiving and giving love as well as to feel appreciated), esteem needs (includes self-respect and enjoying esteem from other people that relevant to them), and lastly, need of self-actualization which is based on the satisfaction at all of the other four levels as it is the highest potential of a person can be. Personally, the need to reach the level of self-esteem and self-actualization starts with acceptance and be comfortable with who you are.

Jain, Gupta & Bindal (2019) suggested types of motivation that urge individuals to give their best and achieve the organization's objectives. 1. Intrinsic motivation, which is a type of motivation where an individual is being motivated by internal factors. 2. Extrinsic motivation, when an individual is being motivated by external desires. 3. Positive motivation, it is where initiates individuals to do work in the most ideal way and to improve their performance. 4. Negative motivation, it aims at controlling the negative endeavors of the work. 5. Reward-based motivation,

a type of motivation that is utilized when you or others know that they will be a reward once a certain goal is achieved. 6. Fear-based motivation, where the word “fear” carries a heavy negative meaning but when it comes to motivation, this is not necessarily the case. And lastly, 7. Achievement-based motivation, to whom are constantly driven to acquire positions and earn titles for themselves are typically dealing with achievement-based motivation. Furthermore, Herzberg saw motivation comes from intrinsic values (Haque et al., 2014) in which I personally agree with this situation. I personally will feel better if I achieve something after making efforts. We are human and we are still learning. Moreover, we cannot expect to know everything. Even if you do not know, it is normal to start somewhere or even start all over.

I can say it was a bit chaotic to carry out our group assignment from the start until the deadline. From the change of our topic, change of plans, and the difference in teamwork dynamic. Further in finishing up with the research proposal, we realized that conducting research about the proposed topic would gain sensitivity to the proposed organization and our society. We had to change the topic from sexual harassment to cyberbullying. Also, due to the current pandemic, we were not able to conduct primary research thus it affects our overall research on what we were initially aiming for. Group assignments were supposed to be a ‘group’ work but sometimes it felt like there is an imbalance of contributions for the assignment, where one would contribute more than the other. However, we got through it and I could never be grateful for my team members. I honestly could have contributed a lot more to this group’s assignments but to the lack of unprofessionalism in time management and execution of my work, I feel that I am lacking in some parts and should have performed better. Towards the end of the dateline, we were driven by our extrinsic values (Amabile, 1993) on how we wanted to do better, earn good grades, and recognition from others. What I gained from this group assignment was patience and better communication skills with the group members and my own self. I learned that action speaks louder than words. Due to one of my groupmates’ lack of professionalism and awareness on the deadline of the group assignment, he/she did not get to submit the report on time in which he/she was initially volunteered to do so. In this view, it would be better if he/she told us in hand whether he/she could not get to submit the work due to personal reasons and we could’ve to understand the situation better. Nonetheless, it would be better if the words have been spoken, actions then took their part. If only we prepare a contingency plan, things would not be as hard because to conduct research is risky. As young researchers, we need to see every element stored in different perspectives and be ready to come up with a proper plan as soon as it subsides. As for the post-project analysis, I acknowledge my other groupmate’s hard work and dedication in completing the assignment. Without his contributions to the group, things would not turn out to be as good. Overall, through ups and downs, everything went well even though there is a mishap towards the end of the project. However, things went right when I got good feedback on using my choice of analytical tool for the group’s project, and I could not have contributed more as I did if nothing drives me to continue the assignments.

For an individual analysis paper, it is more likely the same as the group case study to the point of changing the proposed topic more than up to five times. It is because of fear the data gathered to be thin, irrelevant with current issues and modules, and not rigorous as well as feasible for research analysis. This issue could be common for researchers, but I was overwhelmed until the level of panic. The number of insecurities that took over my mind of what I am doing initially was stressing myself out. The insecurities built up because of not knowing if what I am doing is on the right trail to the point of eating me inside. However, I am glad that this module is using peer reviews. I can learn from my peer’s constructive comments and feedback from Dr. Rozie. The feedback I

received helped me get through this assignment and continue with the rest because it is better to put things moving forward than cling to my personal issues. To overcome my personal issues, I began to look up motivational quotes. One of the strongest quotes by far I had encountered was by Albert Einstein saying, “*Anyone who has never made a mistake has never tried anything new*”. I could never agree more, and it kept me going whenever if I ever made a mistake. Mistakes were made to make us understand the situation and all we can do is learn from it. As my stress reliever, I always make the time to go for indoor cycling at least once a week. Work is work but our mind needs the getaway from being burnt out. Therefore, exercising is the getaway as it has been proved to reduce anxiety and depression as well as improving mental health (Sharma, Madaan, & Petty, 2006). What went right was when I received a small, good feedback such as “good effort”, “well done”, and “Interesting topic with good choice...”. It felt good that somehow these compliments made me think that I am doing the right thing.

I would say one of my personal strengths is multitasking. Multitasking is seen in conducting two or more tasks at the same time (Lin, 2013). One of the author’s findings was multitasking in relation to priority or preference. A good part of this strength in myself is being able to think about something else while focusing on important matters. For example, while focusing on my assignments, I tend to think about my other assignments and eventually contribute the new points. So basically, when I come back to the other assignment, I usually know what to add on because I have the previous points in hand. Other times, when I feel that I am running out of time, I used to do my work wherever I go out with my friends and families. There will be times when I eat quickly or eat while working on my assignments. Sometimes I got to the point where I feel eating was a waste of time and sleeping was just for the ‘weak’ when catching up with the dateline. This type of activity may disrupt focus on different things at different times (Lin, 2013). It may increase the probability of sensing things from multiple channels, but it may not develop deep focus into either one of the tasks unless we make a conscious decision and act. This issue is henceforth related to my second personal strength. I tend to realize where my mistake is and how it can affect my overall performance. As a student, we also need to rest and consume a healthy diet for our overall well-being. In this case, I learned that I must manage time remarkably resulting in a peaceful state of mind and not to put a massive workload in one time.

As for my weakness, I tend to get insecure with the quality of work I have submitted for this module. Often, I get quite discouraged after reviewing my peer’s work and comparing them to my work. The level of caliber of my peer’s work is far better than my work. It makes me think that if the work they handed in is the standard of being a master student, I should double my effort in the near future to reach the standard level or better, because in my book, to reach the standard level is just the bare minimum and people around the world is competing with each other on who is going to be at the top.

Initially in this paper had touched on the personal mindset of being a master’s student who would give the chances of a high salary paid job in the future. However, this mindset changed in time. As time passes by, and with the addition of age to our book, we tend to crave more knowledge and view things from different perspectives. This is completely normal. We are a human being, we live, and we learn. Therefore, we study. We might do not know everything and there is a lot of knowledge that is needed to consider in our lives. My first expectation specifically in this module was to gain insights on understanding organizational behavior. I learnt that it is more than just the study of human behavior in organizational settings and the relation of human behavior with the

organization itself. Even though this module does not directly give out notes, it makes me think that in this level of education, it is normal. It teaches us that our life of being spoon fed days are all over and start to be independent. In other words, find the solution in any ways possible to answer your questions. Ask your peers, friends, and family as well as your lecturer to confirm the things you do not know. There is an old saying, you will lose your way if you are shy to ask. Adapting this method in the earliest stage possible will come in handy when I get into work life in the future. In addition, this module brings out my decision-making skills. Decision making is the process of choosing several alternatives, and by making these decisions, it creates problem solving where it finds the answer to a question (Griffin et. al, 2016). As a master student, we have the power to make decisions every day. This includes, in getting out of bed, start your day and be productive.

In conclusion, I am personally grateful and honored to take this module because I get to learn a lot of facts and insights, resulting in my personal growth. This module might be overwhelming at first where you have this feeling that you need to be top notch and spot on. My ways to keep things balanced are refreshing your goals daily and keeping in touch with what is on the table. If things do not work out as you expected, a 10% of progression is better than 0% nothing. Furthermore, having support from other people is important. Be sure not to push people away because at times, they could be the energy when you needed the most.

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